

Acid Dissociation Constant of Streptomycin Perchlorate and Stability Constant of its Complex with Copper(II)

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The acid dissociation constant of streptomycin perchlorate and the stability constant of its Cu(II) complex have been determined by potentiometric pH titration measurements in aqueous medium maintaining a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M (NaClO₄) at 30°. pK_a for streptomycin perchlorate is found to be 8.00 and log K for 1:1 complex of Cu(II) with this ligand is 3.72.

STREPTOMYCIN, a well known antibiotic, has been studied for its complex forming properties with certain metal ions¹⁻⁴. Zahn and Eisenbrandt² have ascertained, by potentiometric pH titration, the formation of 1:1 complex between streptomycin sulphate and the ion in the alkaline medium.

It, however, seems that no physico-chemical study of the above, as well as other complexes of streptomycin with various metal ions, has so far been carried out. A systematic physico-chemical investigation of this ligand with various metal ions is considered of great interest.

This study presents the determination of pK_a value of streptomycin perchlorate (SMPC) and the stability constant (K) of SMPC - Cu(II) complex by potentiometric pH titration in aqueous solution, maintaining a constant ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄) and temperature 30°.

Material and Methods

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. (AnalaR) quality. Streptomycin perchlorate solution was prepared by treating an aqueous solution of streptomycin sulphate (B.P. grade) with an equivalent quantity of barium perchlorate. The precipitates of barium sulphate were filtered off and the filtrate was diluted to a definite volume.

All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared and standardised by titrating it against a standard solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate⁵.

An "ELICO" model L-10 pH meter (accuracy 0.05) with glass and calomel electrodes was used for titration. Calibration of the pH meter electrode system was carried out with the help of standard buffers. Titrations were performed using a microburette which could be accurately read to 0.01 ml.

pK_a Value: This was determined by titrating 50 ml of 8 × 10⁻³ M solution of SMPC against a

standard alkali solution. 40 ml of 0.01 M aqueous solution of SMPC were mixed with 5 ml of M NaClO₄ and the mixture was diluted to 50 ml. The mixture was titrated against a carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution (0.5 M) with an increase of 0.1 ml and pH recorded after each addition of base. The pH was plotted against the volume of alkali added (Fig. 1).

Only one inflection at 1 mole of alkali/mole of ligand reveals the monoprotonic nature of SMPC. If HA represents the ligand molecule, its pK_a value can be expressed by the following formula.

$$pK_a = - \log \frac{[H^+][A^-]}{[HA]}$$

From the titration curve, the protonation function n_H, the average number of H⁺ ions liberated per ligand molecule, was calculated at various pH values. The protonation curve (Fig. 2) was obtained by plotting the n_H values against corresponding pH. The value of pK_a was directly read from the curve at n_H=0.5.

The pK_a values were also calculated employing the following equation :

$$pH = \log \frac{n_H}{1 - n_H} + pK_a$$

The average value of pK_a was found to be 8.00.

Stability constant of the SMPC - Cu(II) complex: Bjerrum method⁶ as modified by Calvin and Melchior⁷ was followed for calculating the stability constant of SMPC - Cu(II) complex.

Following sets of titrations were performed :

- 20 ml 0.01 M SMPC + 5 ml M NaClO₄ + 1 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 24 ml water
- 20 ml 0.01 M SMPC + 5 ml M NaClO₄ + 1 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 19 ml water + 5 ml 0.02 M Cu(ClO₄)₂.
- 20 ml 0.01 M SMPC + 5 ml M NaClO₄ + 1 ml 0.1 M HClO₄ + 14 ml water + 10 ml 0.02 M Cu(ClO₄)₂.

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Fig 1 : Titration of $8 \times 10^{-8} M$ SMPC against 0.5 N NaOH

Fig 2 : Protonation curve of SMPC

Fig 3 : Titration of SMPC in the absence and presence of metal ions

Fig 4 : Formation curves of SMPC - Cu(II) complex

The total volume in each case was 50 ml and the ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 M NaClO₄ and the metal to ligand ratio was 1:2 and 1:1 in mixtures (B) and (C) respectively. The titration curves of this mixtures against 0.5 M sodium hydroxide are plotted in Fig 3.

The formation curve was obtained by plotting \bar{n} values against pA^- . \bar{n} , the average number of ligand molecule bound per metal ion was evaluated from the horizontal distance, in Fig. 3, between the reference curve (A) and curves (B) and (C) for two different

concentrations of metal ions. The concentration of anion (A^-), of chelating agent, was calculated from the knowledge of pK_a value of SMPC and the pH of the solution. For each calculation, correction was made for increase in volume due to the addition of alkali. The formation function (\bar{n}) has been calculated only upto pH values 7.5, as the solution becomes turbid above this value.

The value of pA^- , obtained from curves A and B, were plotted against corresponding \bar{n} (Fig. 4). These values were corrected by employing Bjerrum method

of successive approximation⁸. The calculated curve was drawn along with the experimental one. From this curve the pA^- value at $\bar{n}=0.5$ was taken to be $\log K$ which came out to be 3.72. Similar result was obtained from curve (C).

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